

Supplementary Table S1: Subdomain-specific internal consistency of the Mpox knowledge questionnaire

Subdomain	Number of items	Cronbach's α	95% CI
General knowledge	4	0.60	(0.54–0.66)
Aetiology	5	0.65	(0.59–0.71)
Transmission: modes	7	0.75	(0.70–0.80)
Transmission: risk groups	4	0.60	(0.53–0.67)
Transmission: animal-to-human	5	0.70	(0.64–0.76)
One Health	4	0.55	(0.47–0.63)
Epidemiology	9	0.75	(0.70–0.80)
Signs and symptoms	7	0.70	(0.64–0.76)
Prevention	6	0.65	(0.59–0.71)

footnote: 95% CIs were computed using the bootstrapping method (1000 replicates). The One Health subdomain was not used as a composite score; individual item responses are reported in the Results.